

THE INFLUENCE OF SOCIAL MEDIA MARKETING TIKTOK ON PURCHASE INTENTION THROUGH EWOM AND CUSTOMER TRUST

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Abstract

The purpose of this study was to determine the impact of social media marketing TikTok on purchase intention via EWOM and customer trust in the clothing products. This study is classified as quantitative research because it collects data through a questionnaire. We gathered information from 420 people using a Google Form survey with multiple parameters. The data was analysed using the SmartPLS tool and the SEM. We discovered that social media marketing had a positive and significant impact on the purchase intention of TikTok Shop clothing products. However, brand image and customer engagement also have an impact on purchase intention. EWOM has the most significant impact as a mediation variabel in improving purchase intention.

Keywords: Customer Trust, EWOM, Purchase Intention, Social Media Marketing, and TikTok.

INTRODUCTION

These days, the trend of shopping through social commerce has begun to shift e-commerce in Indonesia. This is in accordance with Bank Indonesia's statement, that social commerce is one of the reasons for not achieving the realization of e-commerce transaction value throughout 2022 (IDR 476.3 trillion), which is below the target of IDR 498 trillion (Kompas, 2023). Social commerce is the use of social media as a means of promotion and buying and selling directly through applications. Social commerce creates a more interactive shopping experience. Buyers can not only interact with sellers, but can also interact with other users by sharing products, commenting, etc (Kompas, 2023).

TikTok is one of the social commerce platforms that is ranked as the fourth most popular social media. Although it only adapted social commerce in 2021, the platform managed to rank first in the social media most often used for shopping. The percentage of Tiktok Shop users (46%) beats whatshaap, Facebook, and Instagram who have already adapted the feature (Populix, 2022). The most frequently purchased product category on social media is clothing products with a percentage of 61% (Populix, 2022). Clothing is one part of the fashion industry that is growing rapidly in Indonesia. Many local clothing brands in Indonesia are continuously innovating so they are not outmatched by foreign brands. (Liputan6.com, 2022).

The previous explanation indicates that consumers have a high purchase interest in clothing products at TikTok Shop. The high interest in buying clothing products on social commerce shows that sales competition is getting tougher in the industry. The high and low purchase interest is not without reason, of course there are influencing factors. Based on (Indika & Jovita, 2017), SMM has a large and favorable impact on purchase intention. Consumer buying interest

is also influenced by the adoption of information on EWOM (Leong et al., 2022). Meanwhile, according to (Zhao et al., 2020), trust also has a role in user purchase intention.

Social media can effectively maximize revenue through advertising (Forbes, 2022). The adaptation of the Shop feature on TikTok was a response to the increase in sales of various products after brands promoted through the platform (Kompas, 2023). It is even predicted that TikTok for business will become a marketing trend in 2023 (Meltwater, 2023). This shows that social media marketing (SMM) can generate purchase intention. However, the data shows that there may be a decrease in ad reach on TikTok between January 2022 and October 2022 (DataReportal, 2023). Furthermore, research with contradictory findings claim that social media marketing has no substantial impact on customer purchase intention (Satriyo et al., 2021).

Social media marketing via EWOM (Electronic Word-of-Mouth) has the potential to impact customer purchasing behavior (Winarno & Indrawati, 2022). When social media users see a product, they are more likely to talk about it and promote it to other consumers. The amount of consumers that freely share their product-use experience demonstrates EWOM (Winarno & Indrawati, 2022). Most of people like to share their favorite brands on social media (DigitalBisa, 2023). 85% of people like to share brands with friends (Forbes, 2022).

Trust plays a role in influencing user purchase intentions (Zhao et al., 2020). Social media marketing has the potential to improve consumer trust in a product, resulting in a desire to purchase (Winarno & Indrawati, 2022). The rise of issues related to the vulnerability of user data security has led TikTok to be boycotted in many countries (Tribunnews, 2023). In addition, recently there have also been frequent cases of online shopping fraud, one of which is through TikTok Shop. This fraud mode is in the form of sending a link to verify the TikTok Shop buyer's data, containing the login code or password for the TikTok account (Ayojakarta.com, 2023). Meanwhile, confidence in social commerce is strongly dependent on users' perceptions of social media security and privacy, particularly in connection to their personal information (Sharma et al., 2019). So that these problems can certainly lead to user distrust of TikTok.

Researchers are interested in investigating the influence of TikTok SMM on purchase intention for apparel product categories at TikTok Shop using Electronic Word of Mouth (EWOM) and customer trust as intervening factors based on the phenomena presented.

LITERATURE REVIEW AND HYPOTHESES DEVELOPMENT

Marketing

Marketing is the process of recognizing and addressing human and social needs in ways that are consistent with organizational objectives (Kotler et al., 2022:29). Marketing is a function of an organization and a stage in the process of creating, communicating, and delivering value to consumers while also building consumer relationships that benefit the organization and its stakeholders (Priansa, 2017:31).

Marketing Mix

The marketing mix is an internal element that is very important to shape the marketing program (Hurriyati, 2018). The marketing mix describes the actual offering that a business provides in a target market through seven aspects (product, service, brand, pricing, incentives, communication, and distribution) that operate in tandem to build market value for the firm's product (Kotler et al., 2022)

Marketing Communication

Marketing communication is the process through which organizations, both directly and indirectly, inform, persuade, and remind customers about the products or brands they sell. A corporation must build an Integrated Marketing Communication campaign that covers several media in order to communicate its value proposition to its target audience more effectively (Kotler et al., 2022:296). Advertising, events and experiences, public relations and publicity, online and social media marketing, mobile communication, direct marketing, mobile communication, personal selling, and packaging are all part of the marketing communication mix (Kotler et al., 2022:297).

Social Media Marketing

SMM refers to online activities and programs that are aimed to directly or indirectly involve customers or potential consumers by boosting awareness, enhancing image, or generating sales of products and services (Kotler et al., 2022). The characteristics of SMM activities can be classified as follows (Seo & Park, 2018),

Entertainment: result of fun and play acquired through social media, either in the form of words or actions as an entertainer.

Interactions: Social media platforms provide insights into people who contribute to certain brands on social media platforms; these individuals meet and interact with one another in cyberspace and debate specific products and/or brands.

Trendiness: giving the most recent product or service information

Customization: the extent to which customer needs are reflect by services, as well as efforts to adapt products to consumer tastes.

Perceived risk: As a result of customer behavior uncertainty. It has the capacity to ease customer fear or concern.

Electronic Word of Mouth

EWOM is a type of marketing activity that uses the internet as a medium to generate word-of-mouth effects to help businesses and marketers achieve their goals. (Kotler & Keller, 2016:645). EWOM can be seen from the number of consumers who voluntarily share their experience in consuming the product (Winarno & Indrawati, 2022). The information adoption model has been adapted by various studies to examine EWOM variables, one of which is research by (Indrawati et al., 2022) with the following dimensions,

Information quality: relates to the content's quality in EWOM

Information credibility: refers to persuasiveness and where information is considered accurate, powerful, and credible.

Information quantity: The frequency or number of times customers are exposed to information, EWOM, or reviews.

Customer Behavior

The study of how people, groups, and organizations choose, acquire, use, and dispose of goods, services, ideas, or experiences to fulfil or complete their wants and aspirations (Kotler et al., 2022:79).

Purchase Intention

Purchase Intention is a type of consumer behavior in which the consumer wishes to buy or select a product based on previous experience, use, and desire for the product (Kotler et al., 2022). The four dimensions of purchase intention include (Priansa, 2017).

Transactional Interest: Consumers' desire to purchase the firm's goods and services on the basis of their strong faith in the company.

Referential Interest: the propensity of customers to recommend their items to others. This interest develops once buyers get knowledge and experience with the product.

Preferential interest: explains the behavior of buyers who favor certain products over others. This choice can only be altered if the chosen product is damaged.

Explorative interest: characterizes the behavior of consumers who are always seeking information on the things they are interested in, as well as information to back up the favorable features of these products.

Customer Trust

Customer trust is all the knowledge, beliefs, and emotional ties that consumers have regarding a company products (Wibowo & Donni, 2017). There are three dimensions that can be used to measure customer trust, namely (Japariato & Adelia, 2020),

Ability: ability that refer to the competencies of an organization/brand

Benevolence: benevolence is the willingness of the seller to provide mutually beneficial satisfaction for himself and also consumers

Integrity: Integrity refers to the seller's behavior or practices in conducting his business. According to the facts, the information offered to customers is correct.

Hypothesis

SMM affects EWOM. Marketing activity through social media allows products or brands to be widely discussed. In these conversations, consumers share their experiences in using the product or brand. The research conducted by (Winarno & Indrawati, 2022) and (Dewi et al.,

2021), which indicates that there is a positive and significant influence between social media marketing on EWOM.

H1: SMM has a significant and positive effect on EWOM of TikTok Shop Clothing Products

Marketing activity conducted through social media can build consumer trust. Social media allows consumers to search for information to assess their trust in sellers, brands and products. Direct networking, immediate feedback, and content that is more real created by customers is what builds trust in social media marketing (Umair Manzoor et al., 2020) and (Zhang & Li, 2019).

H2: SMM has a significant and positive effect on Customer Trust of TikTok Shop Clothing Products

Promotional activities conducted through social media has an influence on customer purchase intention (Winarno & Indrawati, 2022) and (Indika & Jovita, 2017).

H3: SMM has a significant and positive effect on Purchase Intention of TikTok Shop Clothing Products

EWOM is able to reach a wide community, implementation of EWOM can encourage other potential consumers to make purchases. EWOM is often a consideration for consumers when making purchases (Leong et al., 2022) and (Winarno & Indrawati, 2022).

H4: EWOM has a significant and positive impact on Purchase Intention of TikTok Shop Clothing Products

When consumers already have trust in a product or brand, they will have more than the intention to buy the product or brand. It implies that consumer confidence has a positive influence on purchase intention (Umair Manzoor et al., 2020) and (Japariato & Adelia, 2020).

H5: Customer Trust has a significant positive impact on Purchase Intention of TikTok Shop Clothing Products

Social media users trust other users' reviews and referrals because the information is communicated by users who are previous buyers. Based on research conducted by (Seo & Park, 2018) and (Sulthana & Vasantha, 2019), EWOM has a positive and significant influence on consumer trust.

H6: EWOM has a significant positive impact on Customer Trust of TikTok Shop Clothing Products

Social media marketing can encourage someone to express their opinion on a product or brand that can increase the knowledge of other consumers so that they are willing to inform other colleagues. Users who adopt information on EWOM through social media tend to form purchase intentions. Based on research conducted by (Erkan & Evans, 2018) and (Dewi et al., 2021), EWOM is able to mediate the relation between SMM and purchasing intention.

H7: SMM has a significant positive effect on Purchase Intention of TikTok Shop Clothing Products through EWOM

Trust in social networks is a crucial factor for consumers in choosing social commerce to make purchases. Socialization from social media has a positive influence on consumer trust, which in turn will effectively influence purchase intention. According to (Umair Manzoor et al., 2020) and (Sulthana & Vasantha, 2019), *social media marketing* and trust significantly affect consumer purchase intention.

H8: Social media marketing has a significant positive effect on Purchase Intention of TikTok Shop Clothing Products through Customer Trust

The research model is produced using the outcomes of past studies and the hypotheses that have been formed, as shown in **Figure 1**.

Figure 1 : Research Model

MATERIALS AND METHOD

Based on the aims of the research, this research is categorized as descriptive research with quantitative methods. This research strategy is a survey through a questionnaire distributed online to the sample to obtain data. The sampling technique used in this study is purposive sampling with the criteria that are active TikTok users, have seen the content of clothing products on TikTok, are interested in buying clothing products on TikTok, and follow local brand TikTok Clothing accounts. Researchers use PLS-SEM with smart PLS 3 tools to analyze data which is divided into measurement model (outer model) and structural model (inner model).

RESULTS

From distributing questionnaires online, 420 Tiktok user respondents were obtained who became the sample of this study. Respondents in this study were dominated by women with a percentage of 76% (318 respondents). The majority of respondents are aged 17-25 years, in accordance with data on social commerce users who are dominated by 18-25 years old (67%) according to research (Populix, 2022). 74% of respondents came from the western region of Indonesia, namely Java, Central Kalimantan, West Kalimantan and Sumatra. Most respondents have a final education level of SMA / equivalent and S1 with the profession of students and private employees. The income level of respondents is dominated by the amount of Rp500,000 - Rp3,000,000.

Outer Model Test

Outer model is used to test validity and reliability. The validity test in SEM uses construct validity with convergent validity (loading factor) and discriminant validity (cross loading). The reliability of the data will be known through the reliability test using Cronbach's alpha and composite reliability.

Table 1 : Convergent Validity

Source: Processed Data (2023)

Construct	Indicator	Loading Factor (>0,7)	AVE (>0,5)	Kesimpulan
Social Media Marketing	SM1.1	0.747	0,551	Valid
	SM1.2	0.705		Valid
	SM1.3	0.742		Valid
	SM2.1	0.743		Valid
	SM2.2	0.75		Valid
	SM2.3	0.76		Valid
	SM3.1	0.747		Valid
	SM3.2	0.73		Valid
	SM3.3	0.756		Valid
	SM4.1	0.73		Valid
	SM4.2	0.773		Valid
	Electronic Word of Mouth (EWOM)	EM1.1		0.772
EM1.2		0.759	Valid	
EM1.3		0.801	Valid	
EM1.4		0.785	Valid	
EM1.5		0.81	Valid	
EM1.6		0.802	Valid	
EM1.7		0.806	Valid	
EM1.8		0.786	Valid	
EM2.1		0.804	Valid	
EM2.2		0.78	Valid	
EM3.1		0.797	Valid	
EM3.2		0.799	Valid	
EM3.3		0.813	Valid	
EM3.4		0.782	Valid	

Customer Trust	CT1.1	0.758	0,595	Valid
	CT1.2	0.728		Valid
	CT1.3	0.758		Valid
	CT1.4	0.794		Valid
	CT2.1	0.794		Valid
	CT2.2	0.735		Valid
	CT3.1	0.802		Valid
	CT3.2	0.801		Valid
Purchase Intention	PI1.1	0.762	0,563	Valid
	PI1.2	0.715		Valid
	PI2.1	0.718		Valid
	PI2.2	0.742		Valid
	PI2.3	0.706		Valid
	PI3.1	0.747		Valid
	PI3.2	0.801		Valid
	PI3.3	0.759		Valid
	PI4.1	0.789		Valid
	PI4.2	0.772		Valid
	PI4.3	0.738		Valid

According to the table above, every indicator has a value more than 0.70, showing a significant association between each indicator and each variable. The AVE test is also used to check whether each indicator that monitors a variable is unified (Indrawati, 2015). According to Table 1, each indicator meets the convergent validity standards because the AVE value is greater than 0.50.

Table 2 : Outer Loading

Source: Result of data processing (2023)

Indicator	Customer Trust	EWOM	Purchase Intention	Social Media Marketing
CT1.1	0.758	0.601	0.587	0.536
CT1.2	0.728	0.594	0.570	0.514
CT1.3	0.758	0.625	0.608	0.575
CT1.4	0.794	0.647	0.602	0.586
CT2.1	0.794	0.659	0.636	0.609
CT2.2	0.735	0.586	0.531	0.556
CT3.1	0.802	0.688	0.643	0.616
CT3.2	0.801	0.669	0.623	0.589
EM1.1	0.637	0.772	0.665	0.683
EM1.2	0.630	0.759	0.640	0.668
EM1.3	0.669	0.801	0.668	0.672
EM1.4	0.648	0.785	0.646	0.629
EM1.5	0.664	0.810	0.635	0.643
EM1.6	0.661	0.802	0.652	0.638
EM1.7	0.652	0.806	0.624	0.658
EM1.8	0.629	0.786	0.614	0.646
EM2.1	0.652	0.804	0.672	0.664
EM2.2	0.666	0.780	0.642	0.664
EM3.1	0.665	0.797	0.666	0.644

EM3.2	0.639	0.799	0.656	0.654
EM3.3	0.673	0.813	0.690	0.639
EM3.4	0.641	0.782	0.652	0.594
PI1.1	0.683	0.708	0.762	0.646
PI1.2	0.614	0.632	0.715	0.596
PI2.1	0.579	0.594	0.718	0.579
PI2.2	0.574	0.591	0.742	0.588
PI2.3	0.512	0.543	0.706	0.530
PI3.1	0.569	0.598	0.747	0.541
PI3.2	0.595	0.651	0.801	0.607
PI3.3	0.549	0.598	0.759	0.546
PI4.1	0.555	0.610	0.789	0.578
PI4.2	0.566	0.602	0.772	0.574
PI4.3	0.605	0.632	0.738	0.587
SM1.1	0.538	0.576	0.531	0.747
SM1.2	0.508	0.581	0.550	0.705
SM1.3	0.555	0.611	0.589	0.742
SM2.1	0.552	0.589	0.580	0.743
SM2.2	0.556	0.587	0.591	0.750
SM2.3	0.565	0.597	0.608	0.760
SM3.1	0.606	0.645	0.595	0.747
SM3.2	0.537	0.605	0.563	0.730
SM3.3	0.568	0.633	0.554	0.756
SM4.1	0.533	0.578	0.541	0.730
SM4.2	0.536	0.609	0.561	0.773
SM5.1	0.549	0.639	0.593	0.740
SM5.2	0.560	0.651	0.601	0.744
SM5.3	0.553	0.612	0.587	0.725

According to Table 2, as compared to other constructs, each indicator on the social media influencer variable has a higher correlation in each of the analyzed components. In other words, all markers have a strong discriminant validity.

Table 3 : Fornell Larcker

Source: Processed Data (2023)

Construct	Customer Trust	EWOM	Purchase Intention	Social Media Marketing
Customer Trust	0.823			
EWOM	0.772	0.822		
Purchase Intention	0.779	0.774	0.793	
Social Media Marketing	0.733	0.740	0.731	0.753

According to Table 3, the root value of the AVE value (highlighted in the diagonal table) is bigger than the correlation between other variables (not stated in bold). Based on the results in the table above, it is possible to conclude that the questionnaire utilized meets the discriminant validity criteria.

Table 4 : Heterotrait-Monotrait Ratio

Source: Result of data processing (2023)

Construct	Customer Trust	EWOM_	Purchase Intention	Social Media Marketing
Customer Trust				
EWOM_	0.885			
Purchase Intention	0.849	0.873		
Social Media Marketing	0.806	0.866	0.830	

The value of Heterotrait-Monotrait Ratio on table 4, shows there are no values above 0.9. So, it can be said that the research model formed from the variables above is valid.

Table 5 : Reliability

Source: Result of data processing (2023)

Construct	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability	Kesimpulan
Customer Trust	0.903	0.922	Reliable
EWOM_	0.954	0.959	Reliable
Purchase Intention	0.922	0.934	Reliable
Social Media Marketing	0.937	0.945	Reliable

According to Table 4, each variable indicator has a high level of consistency and trust because the overall variable value for Cronbach's Alpha and Composite Reliability is greater than 0.70.

Inner Model test

R Square

Table 6 : R Square

Source: Result of data processing (2023)

Variable	R Square
Customer Trust	0.691
EWOM_	0.672
Purchase Intention	0.709

The largest R Square value is purchase intention variable at 0,709, which indicates that purchase intention can be described by the variables of SMM by 70,9% while 29,1% is explained by variables outside the study. It also explained that social media marketing has the largest effect on the purchase intention variable. On the brand customer trust, R Square equals 0.691. This implies that the social media marketing variable may explain 69.1% of consumer trust, with the remaining 30.9% explained by other factors that were not investigated.

The R Square for the EWOM variable is 0.672, indicating that the social media marketing variable can explain 67.2% of EWOM, with the remaining 32.8% explained by factors that were not investigated. The R-Square value range is divided into three: 0.67 (strong), 0.33 (moderate), and 0.19 (weak) (Ghozali, 2021), so all of the variables classified as strong.

Path Coefficient

The path coefficient test is used to assess the strength of the independent variable's influence on the dependent variable. The results of the path coefficient are as follows:

Table 7 : Path Coefficient

Source: Result of data processing (2023)

Variables	Path Coefficient
Social Media Marketing -> EWOM_	0.820
Social Media Marketing -> Customer Trust	0.210
Social Media Marketing -> Purchase Intention	0.252
EWOM_ -> Purchase Intention	0.399
Customer Trust -> Purchase Intention	0.264
EWOM_ -> Customer Trust	0.651

The value of path coefficient by table 7, shows the highest value of independent variables that influence purchase intention is EWOM by 0,399. Meanwhile, variable with the lowest influence is social media marketing by 0,252.

Q Square

The model's observations and parameter estimate of variables, dimensions, and indicators were evaluated using the Q Square test. The model is predictive if the Q Square value is greater than zero.

Table 8 : Q Square

Source: Result of data processing (2023)

Variable	Q ²	Conclusion
Customer Trust	0.407	Has a predict relevance
EWOM_	0.418	Has a predict relevance
Purchase Intention	0.400	Has a predict relevance

Table 8 illustrates that all endogenous variables have a Q square value greater than zero or have predictive importance, indicating that this model can be used again with the same settings and measurement assumptions.

Goodness of Fit

Goodness of fit aims to test whether or not a significant influence on the regression model. There are three criteria of Gof, 0,1 (small), 0,25 (medium) and 0,38 (big). The following are the results of GoF calculations using the formula:

$$GoF = \sqrt{AVE \times R^2}$$

$$A = \sqrt{0.584549887 \times 0.690718366} = 0,635$$

The calculation of GoF value is 0.643, which indicate a big GoF criteria. It means that the measurement and structural models in this study are feasible and strong for prediction.

Hypothesis Testing

Hypothesis and significance tests are performed after compared the measurement (outer) and structural (inner) models. The main criteria that can be used to measure significance is the t-statistic value with the statistical significance criteria being 1.64 ($\alpha = 5\%$) and p-values < 0.05 . The hypothesis and significance test outcomes are listed below:

Table 9 : Hypothesis Testing

Source: Result of data processing (2023)

Hypothesis	Path Coefficient	T Statistic	P Values	Result
H1	0.820	35.540	0.000	Accepted
H2	0.210	3.118	0.002	Accepted
H3	0.252	4.718	0.000	Accepted
H4	0.399	5.806	0.000	Accepted
H5	0.264	4.421	0.000	Accepted
H6	0.651	10.117	0.000	Accepted
H7	0.327	5.791	0.000	Accepted
H8	0.055	2.624	0.009	Accepted

Hypothesis 1: The path coefficient for the SMM and EWOM had 0.820 (positive), with a 20.991 T statistic > 1.65 , and 0.000 p value < 0.05 . Hypothesis 1 is proved, which mean social media marketing positively and significantly improve EWOM.

Hypothesis 2: The SMM and customer trust has a 0.210 (positive) path coefficient, with a 3.118T statistic > 1.65 , and 0.002 p value $< 0, 05$. Hypothesis 2 is proved, which indicate that SMM has a positive and significant influence on customer trust.

Hypothesis 3: The path coefficient for the SMM and purchase intention had 0.252 (positive), with a 4.718 T statistic $> 1, 65$, and 0,000 p value $< 0, 05$. Hypothesis 3 is proved, which mean SMM positively and significantly improve purchase intention.

Hypothesis 4: EWOM and purchase intention has a 0.399 (positive) path coefficient, with 5.806 T statistic $> 1, 65$, and 0,000 p value $< 0, 05$. It indicates that EWOM and purchase intention has a positive and significant influence on purchase intention.

Hypothesis 5: Customer trust and purchase intention has a 0.264 (positive) path coefficient, with 4.421T statistic $> 1, 65$, and 0,000 p value $< 0, 05$. It means that customer trust positively and significantly improves purchase intention and hypothesis 5 is proved.

- Hypothesis 6: The path coefficient for the EWOM and Customer trust and had 0.651 (positive), with a 10.117 T statistic $> 1,65$, and 0,000 p value $< 0,05$. Hypothesis 6 is proved, which mean EWOM has positively and significantly improve customer trust.
- Hypothesis 7: The indirect effect of SMM on purchase intention as measured by EWOM has a 0.327 (positive) path coefficient, 5.791 T statistic $> 1,65$, and 0,000 p value $< 0,05$. These results show that SMM influences purchase intention as assessed by EWOM positively and significantly.
- Hypothesis 8: The indirect effect of SMM on purchase intention as measured by customer trust has a 0.055 (positive) path coefficient, 2.624 T statistic $> 1,65$, and 0.009 p value $< 0,05$. These results show that SMM influences purchase intention as assessed by customer trust positively and significantly.

DISCUSSION

The statistical test results reveal that SMM has a 0.820 positive and significant influence on EWOM. The better SMM through TikTok, The bigger the impact on the establishment of a stronger electronic word of mouth of TikTok Shop Clothing products. As specified by Winarno & Indrawati (2022), E-WOM is highly influenced by social media marketing in a positive and significant manner.

Furthermore, social media marketing has a positive and significant influence on customer trust by 0.210. This implies that social media marketing on TikTok can raise customer for TikTok Shop Clothing products. As defined by Umair Manzoor et al (2020), the sociability of social media has a positive impact on the trust of the consumer. Statistical tests show that SMM has a 0.252 percent positive and significant influence on purchasing intention. The more appealing social media marketing of TikTok clothing products on TikTok, the more likely customer purchase intention happens. According to Indika & Jovita (2017), there is a significant influence between social media marketing and purchase intention.

Furthermore, EWOM and purchase intention has a positive and significant (Leong et al., 2022) influence on purchase intention by 0.399. The more EWOM done by TikTok users, the greater the purchase intention for TikTok clothing products. As defined by Leong et al (2022), to increase product purchase intention, information on EWOM can be a major consideration.

According to the findings of the statistical tests, customer trust positively and significantly improves purchase intention by 0.264. This means that customer trust can increase customer purchase intention on TikTok clothing products. According to research conducted by Japariato & Adelia (2020), trust has a direct influence on consumer purchase intention. In the context of online shopping, the relationship between the two is positive. Furthermore, EWOM has positively and significantly improve customer trust by 0.651. This implies customer trust on TikTok Shop Clothing products highly influenced by EWOM that TikTok users done. Research conducted by Seo et al (2020), states EWOM has a significant effect on user trust. The more positive EWOM on social media, the higher the trust.

The outcomes of the statistical test also indicate that social media marketing influences purchase intention through EWOM positively and significantly by 0.327. Customer purchase intention on TikTok Shop clothing products may rise if there is a word-of-mouth effect between TikTok users in social media marketing carried out by brands. According to Erkan & Evans (2018), users who adopt information in EWOM through social media tend to form purchase intentions, where the information has been exchanged among friends.

Moreover, social media marketing influences purchase intention as assessed by customer trust positively and significantly by 0.055. Customer trust in SMM has a small influence on consumer buying interest in TikTok clothing products. Research done by Umair Manzoor et al (2020), states customer trust's significant mediating role between social media marketing and consumer purchase intentions.

Some limitations occurred in this study. Researchers only focus on clothing products as the most purchased products on social commerce. The social media platform studied is TikTok, so there may be differences in results on other social media platforms.

CONCLUSION

Based on the test output, it is possible to conclude that purchase intention on TikTok Shop clothing products are influenced by social media marketing, EWOM, and customer trust that happened in TikTok platform. However, EWOM has the biggest impact in encouraging purchase intention than other variables. Electronic word of mouth effect between TikTok users, is highly influenced by social media marketing done by brands on TikTok. The test result also prove that social media marketing through EWOM can influence purchase intention of customer better than not.

Based on the previous statement, clothing brands can maximize the content owned on TikTok accounts by creating more content that interesting, following trends, and adjusting consumer needs. So that information related to clothing products that is delivered can be understood by users well and create a positive electronic word of mouth effect. Which in turn can generate buying intention in TikTok users for clothing products.

Although SMM, EWOM, and customer trust have been shown to support the hypothesis studied, various factors such as viral marketing, influencer marketing, price, and brand image can be studied in future research to gain a better understanding of purchase intention on clothing products especially on TikTok Shop.

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